

Origins of Thermal Strains in Polyester Laminates

F. R. Jones, M. Mulheron, J. E. Bailey

Department of Metallurgy and Materials Technology, University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH, U.K.

ABSTRACT

The temperature dependence of the linear expansion coefficients α_t and α_l of unidirectional polyester and epoxy glass fibre reinforced composites have been determined. The thermal strains in $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ laminates predicted from these values have been compared to those determined from the curvature of an unbalanced $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beam. Good agreement was found for an epoxy resin based laminate. The level of thermal strain in polyester coupons could not be predicted from the values of α_t and α_l for the dry composite. Small quantities of water increase α_t independently of the softening point of the resin, which accounts for the discrepancy.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical, and thermomechanical, properties of a single unidirectional fibre reinforced ply are highly anisotropic so that typical composite construction involves aligning the fibres at different orientations. When such a composite is subjected to an applied load, low-strain damage in the form of micro-cracks can occur in the plies with their fibres oriented at large angles to the applied load. The transverse cracking behaviour of $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ cross-ply laminates, in which the fibres of the 90° ply are at right angles to the applied load, has been studied extensively (1). The levels of applied strain tolerated before such damage occurs are such that any inherent strains induced during manufacture can substantially reduce this threshold. More specifically curing and/or post-curing at elevated temperatures is often required to optimise the chemical and mechanical properties of the matrix resin. On cooling from this elevated temperature thermal strains develop within the laminate. In a unidirectional laminate they are the result of a mismatch between the thermal expansion coefficients of the fibre and matrix. For angle-ply laminates they result from the anisotropic thermomechanical properties of the individual plies. The thermal strains recorded for cross-ply laminates made using different matrix resins but the same glass rovings showed unexpected differences (2,3). In the latter paper it was suggested that the absence of a whitening effect or a debonding 'knee' in the stress-strain curve for the polyester $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ coupons was due to the thermal strains being greater than the debonding strain. A fuller understanding, therefore, of the origin of the thermal strains in the polyester coupons was required.

It has been shown that, on cooling from a temperature T_1 to a lower temperature T_2 , the thermal strain in the transverse ply in the longitudinal direction of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ composite, $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ is given by

$$\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th} = E_\ell b (\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell) (T_1 - T_2) / (E_\ell b + E_t d) \quad (1)$$

where E_ℓ and E_t are the Young's Moduli and α_ℓ and α_t the thermal expansion coefficients of the unidirectional ply in the longitudinal and transverse directions respectively. b is the 0° ply thickness and a is the 90° ply semi-thickness. T_1 is the temperature at which strain is first built into the laminate. α_t , α_ℓ and T_1 in equation 1 are not normally known but the $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell) (T_1 - T_2)$ term can be obtained experimentally from the curvature of an unbalanced $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate which behaves in the manner of a bimetal strip (1). Timoshenko (4) has derived equation 2 which enables $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell) (T_1 - T_2)$ to be calculated from the measured value of ρ at temperature T_2 and known values of b , d , E_ℓ and E_t .

$$(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell) (T_1 - T_2) = (b + d) / 2\rho + (E_\ell b^3 + E_t d^3) (1/E_\ell b + 1/E_t d) / 6\rho (b + d) \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the radius of curvature of the beam. This technique for determining residual thermal strains eliminates the need for individual measurements of α_ℓ , α_t and T_1 and takes into account any stress relaxations which may occur during cooling. Table 1 shows that the measured thermal strains in epoxy coupons are in agreement with the predicted values from equation 1 whereas those present in polyester coupons subjected to different post-curing schedules do not agree with predictions. We have observed a cooling rate dependence on the curvature of polyester coupons post-cured at 130°C . This accounts for the limited discrepancy in the reported thermal strains for laminates post-cured at 130°C (5) but not the significant differences between the experimental and calculated thermal strains. We have also established (6) that optimum values of the expansion coefficient of the resin (α_m) are achieved within the post-curing times given in Table 1.

MATRIX	CRYSTIC 272			EPIKOTE 828/NMA
$\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ (expt)/%	0.34	0.40	0.45	0.28
$\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ (calc)/%	0.15	0.22	0.26	0.28
$10 \alpha_m / \text{K}^{-1}$	80	66	66	60
Post-cure Temp/ $^\circ\text{C}$	50	80	130	150
Post-cure Time/hrs	15	3	1.5	3
$T_1 / ^\circ\text{C}$	50	80	90	140
$T_1 - T_2 / ^\circ\text{C}$	30	60	70	120
V_F	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.55

TABLE 1. The comparison of Thermal Strains in $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ composites ($b=d$) experimentally from the radius of curvature of a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beam with values predicted from equation 1.

In this paper we report a study of the temperature dependence of α_t , α_ℓ , and α_m and describe a method of determining the temperature, T_1 , at which the thermal strains are first induced in the coupon. From a comparison of experimental and calculated values of $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell) (T_1 - T_2)$ we are able to show that for the polyester laminates small quantities of water significantly modify the values of thermal strain.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The resins used in this study were Crystic 272 (Scott-Bader & Co. Ltd.) and Epikote 828 (Shell Co. Ltd.) since glass fibre reinforced composites incorporating

these resins have been studied extensively (1-3).

Crystic 272 is an isophthalic unsaturated polyester resin cured with 2 p.h.r. (parts per hundred resin) of a 50% methyl ethyl ketone peroxide solution (catalyst M) and between 0.25 and 1.0 p.h.r. of a cobalt naphthenate solution (accelerator E). Samples were allowed to cure at 20°C for at least 24 hours prior to post-curing at 130°C for 1.5 hours.

Epikote 828 is a Bisphenol 'A' epoxy resin and was cured with 80 p.h.r. nadic methylene anhydride (NMA) catalyzed by 1.5 p.h.r. benzyl dimethylamine (BDMA). Curing at 100°C for 3 hours was followed by post-curing at 150°C for 3 hours.

The reinforcement used in the laminates was Silenka 051P 1200 tex E-glass fibres with a silane finish compatible with both polyester and epoxy resins. The fibres are supplied as a roving in the form of a flat tape containing approximately 4,000 fibres, of fibre diameter in the range 10-12 μm .

Resin Samples

The activated resins were cast and cured in 8 mm diameter glass tubes and the resulting rods were cut into 8 mm lengths suitable for determining the expansion coefficient.

Laminates

Unidirectional and cross-ply laminates were prepared by winding the glass fibres onto metal frames and impregnating them with the activated resin using a vacuum assisted technique for the epoxy composites (5) and a two-stage hand lay-up process for the polyesters (2). Samples 200 mm x 10 mm and 5 mm x 5 mm were cut from the 0°/90° and unidirectional laminates respectively and post-cured in an air circulating furnace with a temperature control of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The thickness of the samples was 2 mm.

Measurements

Thermal strain. After post-curing the unbalanced 0°/90° beams (200 mm x 10 mm) supported on a flat metal plate were allowed to cool slowly to 20°C. As the temperature is lowered the beam takes on a curvature and the maximum displacement from the flat, δ , was monitored using a travelling microscope. The radius of curvature, ρ , of the beam was calculated by an iterative procedure using equation 3, where y is the length of the beam.

$$1/\rho = \frac{2}{y} \cos^{-1} [1 - \delta/\rho] \quad (3)$$

The ply thicknesses b and d were measured at several points along the beam and found to agree within ± 0.05 mm. With average values of b and d and measured values of E_b and E_t (6) it was possible to determine $(\alpha_t - \alpha_b)(T_1 - T_2)$ as a function of temperature using equation 2. By cycling the temperature between 20°C and T_1 , the temperature at which the beam became totally flat, it was possible to demonstrate the reproducibility of the results.

Expansion coefficients. The thermal expansion behaviour of the samples was studied over the temperature range -50°C to 150°C using a Dupont 942 Thermo-mechanical Analyzer. This produces a trace of variation in sample length with temperature. The apparatus was calibrated using a standard block of pure aluminium of known expansion coefficient ($\alpha = 23 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$). A heating rate of 2K/min was found to eliminate specimen size effects. During the measurements the apparatus was flushed with oxygen free nitrogen to eliminate possible oxidation effects and to establish reproducible conditions. Since the $\Delta L/T$ thermograms for the samples were found to have a pronounced curvature the expansion coefficient at any temperature, $\alpha(T)$, was calculated from the tangent to the curve. In practice a line was drawn between points on the curve at $T \pm 5\text{K}$. The results presented here are averages of at least 5 individual samples, whose

reproducibility was to within $\pm 3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Since the graphs of $\alpha(T)$ against T are effectively the first derivatives of the $\Delta L/T$ curves, an inflection in the latter should not be confused with penetration of the dilatometer probe into the sample.

RESULTS

FIG. 1. The Temperature Dependence of the Matrix Expansion Coefficient, α_m . Epoxy (■); Polyester, Dry (●); after 2 days in water (◆)

The expansion coefficients of the two resins are presented in Fig.1 as $\alpha(T)/T$ thermograms. As the softening point of the polyester is approached the magnitude of α_m increases. Since the epoxy matrix has a higher softening point or glass transition temperature the curve is linear up to a higher temperature. As shown in Fig.1 we also observed an increase in α_m of the polyester resin after immersion in water for 2 days. After isothermal heating at 100°C for 5 hours the thermogram was found to return to its original shape. The thermograms of the epoxy resin after storage in water for 2 days were indistinguishable from the original. Both the expansion coefficients of the unidirectional laminates, parallel, α_\parallel , and transverse to the fibres, α_\perp , were obtained. The results for the epoxy composite are shown in Fig.2 and those for the polyester composite in Fig.3. These experimental values of α_\perp and α_\parallel have been shown (6) to be in good agreement with values predicted by the equations of Schapery using the measured values of α_m . This demonstrates the consistency of the thermomechanical data reported here.

Since the polyester resin showed unusual behaviour which appeared to be caused by an uptake of moisture, we examined unidirectional coupons which had been soaked in water for 2 days and 4 weeks. The $\alpha_\perp(T)/T$ thermograms for these laminates are also included in Fig.3. It is apparent that α_\perp is increased after immersion in water. After 2 days in water the increase in α_\perp was associated with a weight gain of $0.15 \pm 0.05\%$ which, on isothermal heating at 100°C for 5 hours, returned to its original. The thermogram was also identical to that recorded immediately after post-curing. Further immersion for 2 days produced a similar reversible weight gain and change in α_\perp . A weight increase of 0.15% was also observed when these specimens were stored in air for 5 days.

FIG. 2. Linear Expansion Coefficient for a unidirectional epoxy laminate ($V_F = 0.55$) at various temperatures. Transversely, α_t (●) and longitudinally, α_l (■)

FIG. 3. The Temperature Dependence of the Linear Expansion Coefficients for the polyester unidirectional laminate ($V_F = 0.33$). Dry α_t (●), α_l (■). α_t after immersion in water for 2 days (◆) and 4 weeks (▲)

The experimentally determined δ/T curves for the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beams have been converted into graphs of $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell)(T_1 - T_2)$ against Temperature (T_2) and these are shown in Figs. 4 and 5. Also included are values of $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell)(T_1 - T_2)$ calculated from the measured values of α_t , α_ℓ , and T_1 for each laminate.

DISCUSSION

Equation 1 relates the thermal strain, $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$, to the difference in expansion coefficients, $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell)$, the temperature difference, $(T_1 - T_2)$, and the effective stiffness of the two plies, $[E_\ell b / (E_\ell b + E_d d)]$. Since the ratio E_ℓ/E_t has been shown not to vary significantly over the temperature range considered (6), the thermal strain at any temperature T_2 is related directly to the term $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell)(T_1 - T_2)$. Thus in order to compare the experimental and predicted values of $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ we have presented the results in the form of $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell)(T_1 - T_2)/T$ curves.

Fig. 4 shows the experimentally determined curve from the displacement of the epoxy $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beam. Also shown are computed values from the individually determined values of α_t and α_ℓ shown in Fig. 2 and the known value of T_1 . It can be seen that there is good agreement between the computed and experimental curves showing that the curvature of the beam can be readily predicted from the expansion coefficients of the individual plies. This result lends support to the validity of our analysis.

However, the computed and experimental values of $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell)(T_1 - T_2)$ for the polyester composites do not agree. The results are shown in Fig. 5 where it is clearly seen that the experimental values are larger than those predicted from the measured values of α_t and α_ℓ given in Fig. 3. This result confirms the anomalously high thermal strains outlined in Table 1.

Since it was known that α_t increases with small amounts of absorbed water the 'two day water immersion' results for α_t , given in Fig. 3, were used to calculate a second set of $(\alpha_t - \alpha_\ell)(T_1 - T_2)$ values. These are shown as full circles in Fig. 5 where much better agreement between experimental and predicted values is found. Also shown in Fig. 3 is the increase in α_t with measured water content suggesting better agreement between experimental and predicted values will be possible once the water content of the laminate is known.

We conclude, therefore, that the anomalous thermal strains in these polyester laminates can be explained by the presence of a small quantity of water present in the matrix. The expansion coefficients were determined on small samples which can lose water more rapidly than the unbalanced $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beams. As yet we have not determined the nature of the water in the composite. Since it is not removed from a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beam during 1.5 hours at 130°C it is probably strongly bound to either the resin or the glass fibres. An increase in the expansion coefficient of an epoxy resin and its composites due to absorbed water has been reported previously (7). The epoxy resin used in this study was also found to absorb water but the effects on expansion coefficient were only noticeable after much longer immersion times. What is of interest here is the sensitivity of the polyester resin to small quantities of water.

It has been reported (8) that the statistical nature of the copolymerization during gelation and cure of an unsaturated polyester resin leads to a nodular microstructure of densely cross-linked particles of 50-100 nm in diameter embedded in a less densely cross-linked phase. Light scattering studies (9) have shown interstices of about 5 nm in diameter to be present in highly post-cured unsaturated polyesters. We postulate, therefore, that water can diffuse more rapidly into the less densely cross-linked areas with an increase in α_m and hence α_t . These ideas are currently being investigated.

FIG. 4. Variation of $(\alpha_t - \alpha_g)(T_1 - T_2)$ with Temperature for the Epoxy Composite. The continuous line is experimentally determined from the curvature of the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ beam. The points (○) are calculated from α_t in Fig. 2

FIG. 5. Variation of $(\alpha_t - \alpha_g)(T_1 - T_2)$ with Temperature for the Polyester Composite. The continuous line is experimental. The points are calculated from α_t -dry (○); α_t -wet (2 days) (●) in Fig. 3.

CONCLUSIONS

The anomalous thermal strains present in polyester cross-ply composites have been confirmed by comparing the deflection of a $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ beam with that predicted from the measured expansion coefficients of the individual plies. It is found that good agreement can only be obtained when the chosen values of α_t are those for wet samples. The matrix therefore appears to be sensitive to small quantities of water. Good agreement between experimental and calculated values of beam deflection are observed in the epoxy resin case.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

One of us (MM) thanks the Science and Engineering Research Council for a research studentship.

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